

Publication trends of Internet of Things (IoT) and Schools

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, our lives are constantly affected by the internet and technology and therefore, the Internet of Things (IoT). Thus, schools with IoT-based systems are needed. There are many documents in this subject area, but none in which the publication trend is investigated. In this bibliometric study, 61 of the most accurate documents were collected and analyzed to discover the emerging topic of the “internet of Things and Schools”. Publication trends, documents by type, documents by subject area, and keywords dynamics are inspected in this study. Tracking systems for school vehicles, IoT-based classrooms, and energy-efficient schools are the most up-to-date and trending fields in this subject area. Future research needs to concentrate on the trending topics in order to fulfill the public and technology’s demands.

Keywords: Bibliometric, Publication trends, IoT, School education, Top cited

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the rapid growth of technology and the internet, our lives without them are unimaginable and no longer possible [1]. The internet of things (IoT) is one of the wonders that uses technology and the internet. In 1999, Kevin Ashton, first used the term IoT and defined it as a “global network infrastructure that connects many devices with the internet, to exchange information and make smart recognition” [2, 3]. The internet of things (IOT) is the third wave of the world development of the information industry after computers and the internet [4]. Using the Internet of Things in schools will provide an easier system for teachers, parents, and schools themselves [5].

School bus tracking and arrival time prediction [6], designing IoT applications in secondary schools [7], enhancement of educational services using IoT [8], IoT-based educational activities for energy efficient school building [9], monitoring ambient light conditions of a school using IoT [10], and IoT school attendance system [3] are some recent researches on “IoT and schools”. Therefore, there is a need to know about the publication trend in order to discover the emerging phenomenon in “IoT and schools”.

Bibliometric analysis of scholarly outputs allows quantitatively investigating of a particular study field by understanding its structure, characteristics, and patterns [11]. Therefore, here, the authors are reporting their bibliometric study to discover the publication trends of the Internet of Things (IoT) and Schools. The study is looking for emerging and top keywords for future research.

2. METHOD

There are two main scientific databases: Web of Science (WoS) and SCOPUS. SCOPUS has broad coverage in comparison to WoS [12]. Therefore, the data were collected on July 15, 2021, from the SCOPUS database. There were 61 documents with the title of IoT, or “internet of things” and School/s. The collected data were analyzed by using the “visualization of similarities” (VOS) VoSviewer software [13].

3. Results and Discussions

The result is divided into four parts. The first part shows the publication trends. The second part shows the documents by type. The third part is the subject areas in which the papers were written in. The first part discusses the main keywords.

3.1. Publication Trends

The annual distribution of the IoT and schools’ data set of 61 documents are illustrated in Figure 1. The first paper is published by Xu, et al. [4], entitled “The research of safety monitoring system applied in school bus based on the internet of things”. The paper is mostly about using “IoT” for intelligent transportation systems (ITS) which ensures safe and on-time traveling for school buses.

The most highly cited paper in this field is published by Pocero, et al. [14] entitled “Open source IoT meter devices for smart and energy-efficient school buildings”. This article provides a way for better energy efficiency inside schools. In this case, they provide IoT-based hardware in order to control all school buildings while also providing insights to the overall system design.

By reference to Figure 1 “IoT and Schools” is a trending topic and will most likely be discussed furthermore in the near future. Even with the remaining months of 2021, nine papers have already been published; which is the same amount of publications in the year 2018.

Fig. 1. Publication outputs of “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021

3.2. Documents by Type

Figure 2 shows the document types of “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021. The graph separates the documents by conference papers, articles, book chapters, and review papers. However, conference papers usually have a short time frame from idea to publication, in comparison to articles. Therefore, the 59.0% of conference papers in comparison to 37.7% of articles, is an indicator that “IoT and schools” is an emerging field of study.

Fig. 2. Document types of “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021

3.3. Documents by Subject Area

The documents by subject area of the “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021 are demonstrated in Figure 3. The discussed documents are written in the fields of “computer science”, “engineering”, “social sciences”, “mathematics” and more; that result in “IoT and schools” being a multi-disciplinary subject. This particular attribute makes the subject easier to be discussed. Many fields of study may have addressed “IoT and schools” but it is mostly approached by science-based research areas.

Fig. 3. Documents by subject area of “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021

3.4. Keywords Dynamics

Figure 4 is the overlay visualization of the common keywords of “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021 and their relations according to year. The graph is limited to the top 20 most frequently used keywords; which led to the years 2018-2019. “Internet of Things” is the most widely used word in these documents; however, “GPS”, “students”, “engineering education”, and “energy awareness” are the most up-to-date and trending words in the field of research. These new emerging words indicate that schools with renewable energy sources, on-track transportation systems, and practical education systems, are in discussion.

Fig. 4. Keywords dynamics of “IoT and schools” data set from 2011-2021

4. Conclusions

School bus tracking and children’s safety, engineering education by doing IoT-based research in schools and energy-efficient schools with controllable light, and insights into the overall system design are some of the most important subjects in “IoT and Schools”. In the current study, 61 documents with the title of “IoT and Schools” were collected from SCOPUS databases and analyzed by the VOS. The publication trend shows an ascending chart indicating that “IoT and Schools” is a trending topic and when the documents were divided by type, the conference papers were considerably more than the published articles. All of these indicate that the “Internet of Things and Schools” is a new subject and in its infancy stage. The subject areas show that “Internet of Things” when collided with “schools”, can be a widely discussed field of research, debatable by various disciplines. In this undeniable growth of technology and the internet, it is important for parents, teachers, and schools to synchronize themselves accordingly and be able to operate IoT-based systems and control the school environment with them.

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